

POLAND

POLAND

LEARNING SITUATIONS OF BERDAKH WORKS.

Tleumuratova N.M.

Senior teacher of the National Center for Teaching New Methodologies of
Pedagogues of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7637842>

The 19th century is a period of extremely extensive development of Karakalpak literature. The reason is that during this period, the best classical works were created that introduced the name of the Karakalpak people to the world. In particular, Ajiniyaz's "Bozatau", "Damishler" genealogy, Berdakh's "Shajara", "Khorazm", "Qulen bolis" epics can be mentioned. About this rich spiritual history of our nation, the first President I. A. Karimov's other works, "There is no future without a historical past", we should re-create and honor our history, literature, and language with our own hands. [1;186] A clear proof of this is Berdakh's work "Kulen bolis" in 1950, which was fully voiced in Berdakh's collection, and then it was destroyed as a reactionary work of art against the population that could not be studied. evaluates his personality, actions, deep humanism as a work of historical size

The heritage of Berdakh is being studied with new eyes in the period of independence. Researcher in this field, the late scientist A. Murtazaev, including Kh. Hamidov, S. Bakhadirova, A. Pirnazarov, A. Pakhratdinov expressed his opinion. Academician H. In Khamidov's work "Rukopisnoe nasledie Berdakha" it was thoroughly studied that the poet Berdakh is a great classic poet of the Karakalpak people, a creator of national literary heritage, a great enlightener, an encyclopedist scholar, a national historian who wrote the history of his people for the first time.[2;192]

The number of works written about Berdakh up to this period is more than 300, here, we will discuss and study those scientific works and researches from the point of view of the present time, paying attention to the original copy of Berdakh's works.

Haidar Murtazaev, a well-known scientist who wrote candidate and doctoral theses on Berdaq, Doctor of Linguistics, wrote: "One thing belongs to all of us to regret. Even if it is, we have not been able to correct our common classical heritage in literature, folklore, and art in the national natural copy, give them free and objective opinions, and conduct research. From now on, it is necessary to have the main goal of us and the next generation to fill these gaps»[3;14-15] In fact, valuing and preserving our national heritage, re-evaluating it in its original form, is the most important issue today.

N. Dawqaraev, K. Ayimbetov, O. Kojurov, I. Saguytov were the first researchers of Berdakh's artistic works. At the end of the 60s, starting from the 70s, monographic research on Berdakh's works began to be published as a book. Candidate of history, professor M. Tileo'muratov's "Historical sources in Berdakh's artistic works" (Nukus -1968) and "Karakalpoq sharia - historical source" (Nukus 1995), I. "Desert Nightingale" by Saguytov (Nukus -1974), K. Khudaybergenov's "Obshestvenno-politicheskie vzglyady karakalpakskikh mysliteley XIX i nachalo XX vekov" (Nukus -1975), B. "Creation of Berdakh" by Gurbanbaev (Tashkent-1982), A. In Pakhratdinov's works entitled "Epic works of the poet Berdakh" (Nukus - 1987), several opinions about the life and work of the poet Berdakh were expressed. Regarding Berdakh's large-scale works of art, opinions were also expressed about their historicity. In the 1990s, the poet's work became the research object of doctoral theses. The deceased A. In 1993, Murtazaev defended his doctoral dissertation on the topic "Berdakh's wisdom". This year, his work entitled "Modernity and ingenuity in Berdaq's artistic works" (Nukus - 1993) was published. Berdakh's creativity was deeply appreciated in these works.

Berdakh is a doctor of linguistics, professor A. It was Pakhratdinov. Scientist Berdaq was engaged in the creativity of the poet, and conducted extensive research on the historicity of the poet's large-scale artistic works.

Beginning with Najim Daukaraev, Qally Ayyymbetov, O. Kojurov, N. Japakov, A. Murtazaev, Q. Maqsetov, I. Saguytov, S. Bahadyrova, A. Pakhratdinov, A. Pirnazarov, Academician H. Khamidov, K. Mambetov, etc. scientists have studied enough. All their scientific work serves us as a scientific methodical basis. It is considered one of the main tasks to open the still unexplored aspects of Berdakh's works, to study the embodied aspects of many ideas related to our language, religion, history, programs and deliver them to today's young generations.

In general, the heritage of Berdakh is our inexhaustible spiritual resources, our treasure. Today, in their work, writers, poets, historians and literati are explaining that Berdakh is a national genius poet, historian and great thinker who has a great place in the classical literature of Karakalpakstan.

References:

1. Karimov I. A. There is no future without historical memory. T., 1998
2. Khamidov Kh. "Rukopisnoe nasledie Berdakha" N., 1993
3. Moylovazaev A. Modernity and creativity in Berdakh's works of art. N., 1993

POLAND

CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES

International scientific-online conference

POLAND

4. Tleumuratov M. Historical sources in Berdakh's artistic works. N., 1968
5. Tleumuratov M. Karakalpak poetry is a historical source. N., 1995.

